

Paper 1

MOTHERS AS TRAINERS-AN INCLUSIVE AND SUSTAINABLE APPROACH BY GRACE REFORMED TRUST

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ABSTRACT

This case study was carried out to understand a non governmental organization based in Bangalore which trains children and adults with mild, moderate and severe intellectual challenges. Mothers play an important role in the life of children, especially children with intellectual challenges. Mothers are often subjected to rejection, blame and discrimination when they give birth to a child with intellectual challenges. Grace Reformed Trust popularly known as GRT, visions to help reduce the burden of mothers of children with intellectual challenges who are often left out, distressed physically, mentally and emotionally. This organization was established in the year 2014 by Ms. Lordu Mary. Her passion towards working with children with disabilities began when her daughter had both physical and intellectual challenges. As a mother she was amazed at her daughter's potential and she then wanted to empower many such children and their mothers. She dedicated her life and continues to work for this cause along with her daughter who strives to support children with disabilities.

Keywords: - NGO, Children with Intellectual challenges, Adults with intellectual challenges, Mothers, Trainers, Therapies, Direct support services.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Special schools focus on teaching and imparting various skills to children with physical, intellectual and multiple disabilities. About 31 million persons have intellectual Disability in India out of which about 35.29% belong to the age group of children [1]. The impact of these schools has touched upon many lives and made life altering changes as well as empowered many families. In India families with children with intellectual disabilities face challenges especially in education [2]. In India there is an upward growth in the special school that trains on life skills for children with disabilities [3]. While developing training material it's important to provide research and empirical data [4]. Through community-based partnership more action-oriented impact can be created [5]. Social interaction among children with disabilities is a major factor while training [6]. Parents play a vital role and studies show that inclusive schools improve the social skills of their children [7]. Practicing special education must address various dimensions of it such as the law pertaining to special education, research and statistics focus more on individualized educational program disciplines of students etc. [8]. Initially children were not

assessed for ASD but now below the age of 3 they need to be assessed. [9] Special education is a combination of principles and values with classroom techniques, and advocates for children with disabilities [10]. Studies show that retention in special schools is because of commitment, satisfaction and progress made by the children [11]. Grace Reformed Trust Special school is one such special school in Bangalore, Karnataka who provides life skills training to children with physical, intellectual and multiple disabilities.

2. VISION:

- To help reduce the burden of mothers of intellectually disabled children who are very much distressed physically, mentally, socially because of lack of support from their husbands and family, as well as landlords who do not rent their houses to these families because of their disabled children.
- To help severely disabled children (both mental and physical) to come out of their homes where they are chained and parents are afraid to bring them out of their homes to the school and help them to start living. They would like to accept all those severely disabled children who are dependent on everything.
- To build a community of safe homes for these disabled children and also support the mothers to come and stay in these homes and be with their children till the end of their lives.

3. MISSION:

Our mission is to support 100 underprivileged families to help the intellectually disabled children to learn to live a meaningful life and to help these children's mothers to learn valuable life skills to earn for their livelihood and to provide homes for all these families to live as a community.

4. ORGANIZATION STRUCTURE:

This organization commenced through support from a church with 2 Board members. Currently there are 13 caretakers who are also mothers whose children are in program, one physiotherapist, an account and housekeeping staff.

5. HISTORY:

Ms. Mary, Founder of GRT worked in Sandhesh foundation as a volunteer for five years as her daughter was one of the students in the foundation. Her role involved looking after the children with intellectual disabilities and conducting leisure activities. Ms. Mary witnessed the improvement of the children, she then suggested reaching more children with intellectual challenges in the community. She discussed her ideas with the team and they were positive about it. Ms. Mary then volunteered to do data collection and encouraged many underprivileged families to send their child with intellectual challenges to the center. This showed a positive increase in the admissions and gradually children from well economic backgrounds approached the foundation. But unfortunately, the well-to-do families did not want to join the training in which underprivileged children were trained. Looking at the economic status of the underprivileged, Ms. Mary suggested that the training could be given with no charge or fees. This then contradicted the heads of the institution. Ms. Mary then left that institution and brought

her daughter back to her place. She did not want to sit idle hence she decided to look after 2 children with intellectual challenges all by herself. She did not charge any fees for this service. She trained the bedridden babies in physiotherapy and the babies are now able to sit and maintain posture. As a mother of a child with severe intellectual disability she used her experience and trained the other children. She then requested her Church trustees to provide some space of the church for her to be able to look after more children. The Church trustees agreed and gave her a room. Currently there are 35 children with severe and mild intellectual challenges in the center who are trained by their own mothers. The training is focused to reach many underprivileged children, free of cost.

6. CURRENT PROJECTS:

GRT special school projects and programs include:

1. Providing life skills and social skills training to the children- Currently about 35 children between 3 years to 45 years of age join their training and get trained on various skills.
2. Physiotherapy - Apart from imparting life skills, physiotherapy is a must for every child, hence, GRT offers physiotherapy sessions for all the children to strengthen their stability and agility.
3. Bio- Enzyme unit- GRT is run by mothers of some of the children with disabilities, hence, a bio enzyme unit is established to create a self-help group among mothers who can generate money from this unit.
4. Family sessions conducted by a rehabilitation psychologist in collaboration with Diya foundation-to support family members under various areas.
5. Provide a mid-day meal every day for the children and also include them in tasks like cutting vegetables, etc. to help them develop their cooking skills.

7. CASE STUDY BY TWO MOTHERS WHO PLAY A ROLE OF TRAINERS IN GRT:

Ms. Deepa, mother of Ms. Reena (name change) who joined GRT 7 years back has gained a lot of insights as to her daughter's disability and how to work with her daughter. As Ms. Deepa plays multiple roles - a mother and a vocational trainer, she has realized the purpose of herself and her daughter. She's working with her daughter to build her capacity to live her life independently. Ms. Shameem mother of Mr. Abdul (name change) feels proud of her son who is interning in a company as a Service staff and earns money to support his family. She never thought her son would travel independently, follow instructions and company rules and earn money. Now, she continues her training to other children and adults in GRT and motivates them with her story of change.

8. ABCD ANALYSIS:

ABCD analysis is one of the effective tools to analyze the organization on various grounds such as effectiveness of ideas, studying the organization's challenges and how to overcome them [12]. ABCD stands for Advantages, Benefits, Constraints and Disadvantages as constructs for this tool which helps to determine all the key areas through understanding the determinants issues with possible action plan [13]

Determinant issues	Key attribute of a determinant issues	Advantages	Benefits	Constraints	Disadvantages
Unplanned training	Lack of Professional trainers and require additional physiotherapist	Structured training and individual focus will be attained by the trainers	Children and Adults with intellectual challenges can benefit better in terms of individual attention and more on their strengths	Salary for professional trainers and additional physiotherapist	They have a total of 35 students and their ages range from 3 years to 44 years old. Delivery of age-appropriate classes for all is not as effective as there are limited trainers.
Delayed training	Transportation	Students can attend sessions on time and not miss their training	Students can gain more Daily living classes and become self-defendant	Additional cost of travel such as Petrol, Maintenance	Quality use of time is not there as classes begin late, routine gets affected and also there is a need for a trained special educator to lead the others.

9. ACTION PLAN:

Below are some of the action plan for GRT after working the ABCD analysis

- A. Building social media- So far, GRT's impact is witnessed through word of mouth and by spreading the impact through peers and relatives. In the long run, it's important to strengthen the reach of this organization. One way to achieve this by regularly sharing the impact created by the organization on social media. An active and strong social media accounts on Facebook, Website upgradation, Instagram, LinkedIn could be used.
- B. As there are about 35 children and about 10-13 caretakers on an average, most of the time is invested in looking after the children, hence other deliverables could be difficult to meet such as reporting / writing proposals/ attending webinars / building capacity of staff etc. One of the suggestions is to reach out to various colleges and encourage internship / volunteering opportunities. Many young adults or college students are looking for opportunities to work directly with the community and support in all possible ways.
- C. Networking opportunities - As GRT is a budding organization in this field, one way to build a network is to tie up with similar organizations who share the similar vision i.e. to work for children / adults with intellectual challenges. The collaboration could be to build staff capacity building, project management, learning tips and understanding a healthy, professional style of approaching companies for funds. Trainers are getting trained by another organization on early intervention, project management and coordinating projects.
- D. Build up vocational prospects in GRT- to develop skills of the children as well as the mothers in order to help them be financially stable. Training can be provided to develop skills in these areas such as embroidery, painting, crafts, candle making, computer unit, etc. Bio enzyme unit has been initiated in GRT premise and marketing the products to

customers, employability training has been given to the employable candidates from GRT and some of them have received internship and full-time employment opportunities with a hospitality company.

- E. Transportation- Encouraged parents to use public transportation hence, transportation service could be given to those who are in need of it.

10. CONCLUSION

Indian history has a major impact on perception about disability and people with disabilities.[6] GRT in such a short commencement has reached 100+ beneficiaries and as their capacity is being built for betterment, the organization will continue to serve the purpose and empower many children with disabilities. At the same time, mothers of these children play a vital role in this process. These children come from an underprivileged community and hence the organization provides the training without any charges. The mothers get to learn a lot about how to train their child to be independent and become empowered as any neurotypical person. Institution leaders and special educators must go hand in hand to implement inclusive education [14]. Along with inclusive education, transition into the mainstream is also important [15]. Inclusive education also requires training staff and educators in both school level and advisory level [16]. Inclusive education is essential reading for educators, researchers, law makers, psychologist, social workers, all those who are necessary for implementing laws and schemes for inclusive education [17]. Special education is expanding in the education system [18] Special schools will be able to equip more students with adequate resources and trained people. [19] Inclusion helps in reducing anxiety when children with special needs are in mainstream [20]

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